

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of L-Arginine by Potassium Permanganate in Moderately Concentrated Sulphuric Acid Medium

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The rate of oxidation of L-arginine by potassium permanganate in moderately concentrated sulphuric acid media is proportional to the concentration of L-arginine. The total order of the reaction is two at a given concentration of sulphuric acid. The reaction is acid catalysed and the rate is related to the activity of water and also to the acidity function. Primary salt effect is nil, but at higher concentration of neutral salts the logarithm of the rate constant is linearly related to ionic strength. Specific ionic effects have also been investigated. Activation parameters have been reported and the mechanism, pertinent with the observations has been suggested.

ALTHOUGH permanganate is amongst the most versatile oxidants in organic chemistry¹⁻⁴, the kinetic study of permanganate oxidation of amino acids has received but little attention⁵⁻¹³ and no work has been reported on the oxidation of L-arginine by potassium permanganate. The present paper, therefore, deals with this problem.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR or S.M., G.R. grade. L-Arginine was S.M. Biochemical. Potassium permanganate solution was prepared as given by Vogel¹³. Double distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions.

The reactants were left in a thermostat to attain the desired temperature before the final mixing. The kinetics were followed by removing requisite aliquots of the reaction mixture at suitable intervals and estimating iodometrically the unreacted permanganate in them.

Results and Discussion

Order of reaction :

It is observed that at constant concentrations of sulphuric acid and substrate, the order of the reaction with respect to permanganate is one. Plots of $\log(a-x)$ against time indicate two stage processes and both the stages are linear. This indicates that the order of the reaction with respect to permanganate is one for both the stages. Although the details regarding occurrence of the two stages can not be furnished at present, it might be suggested that these stages are probably due to creation of optimum concentration of some intermediate product or due to autocatalysis. Constancy of pseudo first order rate constants, k_1 , for various concentration of potassium permanganate has been observed (Table 1).

TABLE 1— VARIATION OF THE RATE CONSTANT WITH CONCENTRATION OF $KMnO_4$ at 30°
[L-Arginine] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[H_2SO_4] = 1M$

	$10^4 [KMnO_4]/M$				
	4	5	6	7	8
$10^4 k_1/\text{min}^{-1}$ (for I-stage)	2.53	2.54	2.54	2.55	2.53
$10^4 k_2/\text{min}^{-1}$ (for II-stage)	17.21	17.34	17.29	17.39	17.42

Plots of rate constants against amino acid concentrations give straight lines passing through the origin. This shows that the order of the reaction is one with respect to amino acid in sulphuric acid medium for both the stages. There is no kinetic evidence for intermediate complex formation between substrate and permanganate¹⁴ and if any complex is at all formed, its formation constant would be extremely small¹⁵. The results are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2— VARIATION OF THE RATE CONSTANT WITH CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATE AT 30°
 $[H_2SO_4] = 1M$; $[KMnO_4] = 5 \times 10^{-4}M$

	$10^4 [L-Arginine]/M$				
	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5
$10^4 k_1/\text{min}^{-1}$ (for I-stage)	1.36	2.54	3.74	4.88	5.94
$10^4 k_2/\text{min}^{-1}$ (for II-stage)	7.78	17.34	29.75	41.45	53.89

Effect of acid concentration and acid catalysis :

In general, amino acids exist predominantly as the protonated species in concentrated acidic media according to the following equilibria¹⁶.

Increase of acid concentration causes rapid increase in the reaction velocity (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF INCREASING CONCENTRATION OF ACID ON THE REACTION RATE AT 30°

[L-Arginine] = 5×10^{-3} M, [KMnO₄] = 5×10^{-4} M

	[Acid]/M					
	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75	2.00
10 ³ k ₁ /min ⁻¹ (for I-stage)	1.70	2.54	3.17	4.60	6.14	8.42
10 ³ k ₁ /min ⁻¹ (for II-stage)	10.51	17.34	22.51	35.74	50.39	71.19

In the case of oxidation of alcohols by permanganate, it was suggested that the faster rate of oxidation in more concentrated sulphuric acid is most probably due to the protonation of the oxidant in accordance with equilibrium (3), supported by spectral studies^{4b}.

Similar observations in the present case lead us to suggest that HMnO₄ is the active oxidizing species. Also the fact that the rate of oxidation is strictly proportional to the concentration of the substrate indicates that HMnO₄ oxidizes the substrate directly¹⁷.

The two Zucker-Hammett plots, log k against H₀ and log k against log [acid], are linear for both the processes. This shows that the reaction is acid catalysed. However, none of the plots produces the ideal slope of unity. A summary of the various Zucker-Hammett plots¹⁸ is reported in Table 4.

TABLE 4—CORRELATION OF RATE WITH ACID CONCENTRATION

Correlation	Parameter	Slope	
		I Stage	II Stage
Zucker-Hammett plots			
i) H ₀ against log k		0.906	1.08
ii) log [Acid] against log k		1.5	1.88
Bunnett plots			
i) log k against log a _{H₂O}	ω	21	25.7
ii) log k-log k _A against log a _{H₂O}	ω _a	6.66	6.87
iii) ω _a -1.6	ω*	5.06	5.27
LFER plot			
i) log k against -(H ₀ + log [HX])	φ	2.25	2.51

In view of these departures from ideal values, applicability of Bunnett's hypothesis was tested (Figs. 1 and 2). A difficulty in the determination of ω* values with respect to reaction in sulphuric acid is that the extent of acid dissociation of bisulphate

Fig. 1. Bunnett plots at 30°.

Fig. 2. LFER Plots at 30°.

ion in the region of perhaps 0.5 to 3 M is not known. Hence, for the reaction occurring in sulphuric acid below 3.5 M, the ω_a parameter can be determined from the slope of a plot of log k-log k_A vs log a_{H₂O}. ω_a may be converted roughly into ω* values by subtracting 1.6, where log k_A is the logarithm of rate coefficient for acetophenone

enolization as interpolated from the data of Zucker and Hammett¹⁸. A summary of the slopes (ω , ω_a , and ω^*) for the two Bunnett plots are given in Table 4. According to Bunnett's empirical observations the values indicate that the water molecule should act as a proton abstracting agent in the rate determining step^{19(a)}.

The observed data (Table 3) are correlated quite well with the linear free energy relationship (LFER) by the equation

$$\log k = \phi (H_0 + \log [HX]) + \text{constant}$$

proposed by Bunnett and his coworkers²⁰ for basic substrates. The slope of correlation plot of $\log k$ with $(H_0 + \log [HX])$ (Fig 2) constitutes a parameter, ϕ , which characterises the kinetic response of the reaction to changing acid concentration. The ϕ parameters obtained (> 0.58), (vide Table 4) further lead us to confirm that the role of water molecule in the rate determining step is as a proton abstracting agent^{20(b)}.

The values of Hammett's acidity function, H_0 , and logarithm of activity of water corresponding to given acid concentrations have been taken from Paul and Long²¹ and Bunnett^{19(b)}, respectively.

Effect of temperature :

The reaction was studied at 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45°. Energies of activation ΔE^\ddagger , entropies of activation ΔS^\ddagger , and frequency factor, PZ, for the reactions are summarized in Table 5.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR L-ARGININE AT 30°
[H₂SO₄] = 0.75 M ; [L-Arginine] = 5 × 10⁻³ M ;
[KMnO₄] = 5 × 10⁻⁴ M.

Process	ΔE^\ddagger k. cal mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger cal mole ⁻¹ k ⁻¹	PZ litre mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
I-Stage	12.36	-30.50	1.368 × 10 ⁹
II-Stage	5.813	-48.54	1.612 × 10 ⁹

Neutral salt effects and the effect of ionic strength:

No primary kinetic salt effect was observed by adding neutral salts within the concentration limits demanded for the application of Brønsted-Bjerrum equation. At higher concentrations of added neutral salts the logarithm of the rate constant is linearly related to the ionic strength. This is in accordance with equation (4) proposed for the higher concen

$$\log k = \log k_0 + (b_0 + b_A - b^*)\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

tration ranges of the added neutral salts²², b_0 , b_A , and b^* are constants and are largely empirical.

The linear plots of $\log k$ against μ (Fig. 3) show that equation (4) is fairly applicable in the present case, and that the reaction involves two neutral molecules or a neutral molecule and an ion²² in the rate determining stage. The positive salt effect further indicates that the reaction is between a positive ion and a molecule²³.

Specific ionic effects :

If the reactive molecular species or activated complex formed are either charged or dipolar in nature, a specific influence of added cations and anions on the reaction velocity may be expected, depending upon their charge, size, complexing tendency and general nature. In order to investigate the specific effect of cations and anions on the reaction velocity, sodium salts of anions and sulphates of cations were taken at their identical molar concentrations. The order of effectiveness of the anions can be given by the series, $\text{HSO}_4^- > \text{ClO}_4^- > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-$, and in the case of cations the order of effectiveness is $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plot of ionic strength against $\log k$ at 30°.

An examination of Fig. 3 shows that the effect on the rate due to added neutral salts is due predominantly to the cations, the nature of the anions having little effect. Thus, the rate is better correlated with the concentration of a specific cation than with an anion. This specific effect of cations might be due to incorporation of a cation into the activated complex²⁴. It is also possible that the specific cationic effect is due to the more generalised influence of the reactants and atmosphere on the activity coefficients of the reactants and activated complex. It may also be reasonable that cations having different ionic radii might affect activity coefficients, and therefore rates, differently²¹. Berigener and Gindler²⁵, in discussing kinetic effects of added inert electrolytes, concluded that the choice is difficult from kinetic data only, if not impossible. Mishra and Gupta²⁷ and others²⁸⁻³¹ have interpreted specific effects of anions and cations in terms of bridging which facilitates or retards electron transfer in redox systems. From our data and above interpretations, we may suggest that the specific effects of anions and cations depend more or less on their nature i.e. various physico-chemical properties and also on their complexing tendency.

Mechanism :

The products of oxidation were ammonia, CO₂ and aldehyde. The induced reduction of mercury(II) chloride²² in this system indicates that a reducing intermediate is formed. Faster rate of oxidation of L-arginine by potassium permanganate with increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid is due to the production of an active oxidizing species HMnO₄^{4b}. The values ω, ω* and φ parameters suggest that water molecule acts as a proton abstracting agent in the rate determining step. Aldehyde as reaction product may be explained by assuming the attack on carboxylate ion and fission of O-H bond occurring in the rate determining step. HMnO₄ does accept an electron from O-H bond rupture to give rise to free radical and the proton is abstracted by water. If, however, C-H bond fission occurs the product would be entirely different.

In accordance with the experimental results and above discussion the following mechanism is suggested.

where R = $-\text{HN}=\text{C}-\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_5$ and HMnO₄⁻ degrades with respect to oxidation states of Mn(VI) to Mn(II) as follows,

which could be written as :

The above mechanism leads us to give the following rate expression.

$$-d[\text{MnO}_4^-]/dt = k[\text{amino acid}][\text{MnO}_4^-] \quad \dots (13)$$

$$\text{where } k = \frac{k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 \text{H}_2\text{O}}{1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (14)$$

Similar mechanism for one equivalent oxidative decarboxylation have been proposed by many workers^{11,17,23-25}. Step (9) resembles the one proposed by Rosenblatt and coworkers²⁶.

In the present case, the oxidation takes place in two stage processes. Second stage is faster than the first stage process. Intermediate product formed during first stage process after achieving an optimum concentration starts getting oxidized by the permanganate, forming second stage process. The suggested mechanism is further supported on the basis of similar arguments that have been put forth by Levitt and coworkers²⁷ for the two stage process observed during oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by persulphate.

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